

Agroforestry in Andalusia

Stakeholders Policy challenges

- Agroforestry, CAP, aims and Sustainable Development Goals
- Bureaucratic burden
- Legislative adaptation to the territory
- The Bio-District: a new proposal for a strong cooperation to serve environment
- Local, European and CAP policies
- Administrative barriers (bureaucratic burden, poor coordination, etc.)
- Bureaucratic obstacles in accessing land
- CAP (does not consider agroforestry adequately) and Business models: lack of accompanying measures to achieve a transformation from good practices
- Forest fires: low investment in prevention
- Lack of specific funding mechanisms
- Failures in the Agri-Food Chain Law (lack of transparency, fraud, etc.)
- Regulations (limitations, restrictions, prohibitions, not adapted to citizens' needs, complexity, constant changes)"

Policy recommendations

- 1.- Development of working groups to fit funds to existing challenges, reduce bureaucracy at minimum and adapt the legal framework for agroforestry practices implementation in both forest and agricultural land uses.
- 2.- Develop advisory systems linked to global and local research.
- 3.- Establish a short, intermediate and long term strategy to ensure agroforestry transition based on knowledge and digitalization.
- 4.- Understanding agroforestry as a land management ecosystem services provider and a value chain promotion linked to the use of the territory.
- 5.- Better understanding between the different ministries (i.e. environment and agriculture).

STATE:	Spain		Permanent crops	5,02%	6,63%
Nut level:	2		Agroforestry	13,65%	16,57%
Eurostat code:	ES61		Shrubland	20,89%	10,83%
Area (km ²):	86.781		Grassland	7,63%	10,26%
Population	2018	2022	Agroforestry Practice Cover	2018	2022
Population	8.396.464	8.511.185	Silvopasture	13,42%	16,00%
Density (p km ⁻²)	97	98	Agrisilviculture	0,18%	0,27%
Cover data	2018	2022	Agrosilvopasture	0,00%	0,05%
Forest	26,56%	10,48%	Kitchen gardens	0,06%	0,25%
Arable land	14,09%	18,25%			

Holding type	2016	2023
Natural person (ha)	2.772.150	-
Legal person (ha)	1.518.230	-
Group holding and Common land unit (ha)	-	-
Natural person (holder)	227.990	-
Legal person (holder)	16.310	-
Group holding and Common land unit (holder)	-	-

Regional Agricultural Area	Used	2016	2023
Farm number		244.300	-
Farm ha (UAA)		4.290.380	-

Animal populations (Thousand head)	2018	2023
Live bovine animals	533	478
Dairy cows	61	56
Non dairy cows	212	207
Live swine, domestic species	2.625	2.633
Live sheep	2.214	1.800
Live goats	1.030	852

CROPS (Hectares)	2016	2023
Utilised agricultural area	4.290.380	-
Cereals for the production of grain (including seed)	752.510	-
Common wheat and spelt	135.680	-
Durum wheat	278.700	-
Rye and winter cereal mixtures (maslin)	13.030	-
Barley	117.350	-
Oats and spring cereal mixtures	106.090	-
Grain maize and corn-cob-mix	27.060	-
Rice	33.900	-
Dry pulses and protein crops for the production of grain	37.100	-
Industrial crops	350.640	-

Cotton seed and fibre	56.130	-
Other oilseed crops n.e.c.	-	-
Fibre crops	-	-
Aromatic, medicinal and culinary plants	7.260	-
Plants harvested green from arable land	54.030	-
Green maize	5.160	-
Kitchen gardens	100	-

Rural Development Interventions promoting agroforestry

ENVCLIM(70) - Environmental, climate-related and other management commitments

Interventions	2
Forestry	1
Crop diversification including woody perennials	0
Crop rotation including woody perennials	1
Livestock including woody perennials	0
Woody perennials to reduce soil erosion	0
Woody perennials to add organic matter	0
Woody perennials to reduce soil chemical contamination	0
Animal welfare using woody perennials	0
Permanent Grasslands with woody perennials	0
Agroforestry on Permanent Crops	0
Interventions	2

References

Coverland data and Agroforestry practice cover: EUROSTAT LAND COVER/USE STATISTICS (LUCAS). <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/lucas/database/primary-data>
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 Population on 1 January by age, sex and NUTS 2 region (demo_r_d2jan) https://doi.org/10.2908/DEMO_R_D2JAN
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 CAP Strategic Plans by country https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/cap-my-country/cap-strategic-plans_en#cap-strategic-plans-by-country

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